

Facing up to the challenges faced by pre-service teachers in developing learning progressions in Mathematics

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This paper aims to draw attention, via presentation and plenary discussion, to observed challenges faced by pre-service primary teachers when attempting to craft short-term learning progressions in Mathematics in preparation for School Placement (SP).

Keywords: Assessment for learning; teacher education; learning progressions

It is conjectured that, in Ireland, Department of Education (DE) (2023) minimum grade level entry requirements of 30% < 40% at Higher Level (HL) or 60% < 70% at Ordinary Level (OL) in Leaving Certificate Mathematics to access Bachelor of Education (BEd) and Professional Masters in Primary Education (PMPE) degree programmes gives hostages to fortune given the expectation that graduates will be competent to teach mathematics competently. Justification for this statement is based on experience of (a) teaching pre- and in-service modules on Assessment for Learning (AfL) to BEd and PMPE students and (b) evaluating their application of key AfL strategies in SP schemes and lesson plans. It is proposed that greater understanding and acknowledgement of the underlying content and pedagogical knowledge needed by novice teachers to develop appropriate learning progressions, even for relatively short periods of instruction, is needed urgently. Hence, the intended audience for this paper is teacher educators and curriculum developers with responsibility for developing pre-service teachers' capacity to translate curriculum aims and objectives in Mathematics into sequenced learning progressions.

While the term 'learning progressions' connotes different meanings depending on whose work is read (e.g., Shepard, 2018; Aulls, Harley, Getahun, & Lemay, 2020), defining features have been identified which are noteworthy. First, learning progressions detail the 'typical' sequence in which relevant knowledge, skills and competencies develop in a given domain. The expectation is that they provide a blueprint that can be adapted when planning for individual needs and capabilities. Second, the sequences are incremental in nature, i.e., they represent increasingly sophisticated learning as captured by the use of Bloom's (1956; Gogus, 2012) taxonomies of verbs, for example. Third, they focus on what is to be learned/mastered as distinct from how such learning is to be scaffolded (i.e., the conditions of performance to be used such as the resources and methodologies to be employed) (Black & Wiliam, 1998).

While it is axiomatic that learning involves progression, however small or insignificant this may appear (e.g., when working with pupils with moderate, severe and profound difficulties), enabling planned, incremental, vertical learning assumes knowledge of typical learning trajectories in defined domains. Linked with this, pedagogical expertise is required to determine the nature and extent of current performance relative to the overall learning outcomes as well as the capacity to 'close the gap' (Sadler, 1989). This is achieved by employing AfL strategies, notably reciprocal formative feedback between teacher and learner that drives assessment, learning and teaching decisions in real time.

In order to underscore how challenging this can be for pre-service teachers, particularly those pursuing a BEd or PMEP qualification with minimum performance in LC Mathematics, this paper focuses on a unique approach used with pre-service student teachers aimed at elucidating the steps involved in creating a short-term learning progression in a non-curricular domain. For the purposes of illustration, driving a car safely, something which the majority of pre-service have demonstrated knowledge and skill, is used. How this process may be applied in planning to teach Mathematics on SP such that informs both the sequencing of learning a priori, as well as the translation of incremental learning steps into inform daily learning intentions, conditions and criteria of performance, is explained. Attendees are invited to critique the approach adopted and consider its implications for curriculum development and teacher education.

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